

CIVIC EDUCATION: A BASIC REQUIREMENT FOR SUSTAINING CONSTITUTIONAL DEMOCRACY

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Abstract

There is hardly any country including the United States of America, that has achieved the level of understanding and acceptance of rights and responsibilities that is required for maintenance and improvement of constitutional democracy among the totality of its citizens. The paper examines the relevance of civic education in sustaining constitutional democracy. It affirms that democracies are sustained by citizens who have the requisite knowledge, skills and dispositions. More importantly, political knowledge, skills as well as depositions and virtues that inform democratic ethos, are not inherited, but rather learnt. Some of the strongest recommendations of the paper are: community service should be made an integral part of civic education, the importance of civic education should be communicated to the general public through televised public for a print media, parents and civic leaders; participatory methods of teaching is more germane to the success of civic education programme and that capacity building programme should be organized for civic education teachers at all levels.

Keywords: *Civic Education, Requirement, Constitutional Democracy*

Introduction

Educators throughout the world are recognizing that civic education is centered on teaching and learning the principles and practices of democratic government and citizenship. Its interrelatedness and core components are civic knowledge, civic skills and civic virtues or dispositions. Since 1980s there has been a global resurgence of democracy. In various regions of the world,

people of different countries and cultures emphatically have approved of democratic principles and practices. They have recognized that effective civic education is an indispensable means to the establishment and maintenance of democratic ideals and institutions.

Civic education is essential to sustaining constitutional democracy anywhere in the world. Democracy is not a "machine that would go on itself", but must be consciously nurtured and reproduced from generation to generation (Przeworski, 1995). The habits of the mind (knowledge) as well as "habits of the heart" (skills) dispositions and virtues that inform democratic ethos are not inherited but rather learnt and developed. The knowledge, skills and dispositions that undergird a constitutional democracy should be nurtured and sustained.

Civic education, therefore, is or should be a prime concern. There is no more important task than the development of an informed, effective and responsible citizenry. Democracies are sustained by citizens who have the requisite knowledge, skills, dispositions and virtues. Absence of a reasoned commitment on the part of its citizens to the fundamental values and principles of democracy, a free and open society cannot succeed (Putnam, 1993). It is imperative therefore that educators, policy makers and members of civil society make the case and ask for the support of civic education from all segments of society and from the widest range of institutions and government.

Egwu (2008) notes that the re-introduction of civic education into Nigerian school curriculum has come at the most auspicious moment in our country's democratic history. Egwu notes that this is a time when government is making effort not only to savour unprecedented years of interrupted democratic practices but to re-introduce measures to further deepen and strengthen democratic culture.

Conceptual Clarification

Constitutional Democracy

Literally, constitutional democracy is the combination of constitutionalism and democratic terms. Thus, it is useful to see what constitutionalism and democracy are. The Oxford English Dictionary explains that the first use of the word "Constitutionalism" was in 1832 (Gordon, 1999). Constitutionalism means that the coercive power of the state is constrained (Gordon, 1991). Meanwhile the origin of the word "democracy" is from the Greek which consists of two words. These words are "demos" (the people) and "kratos" (rule and authority), (Gordon, 1999). Basically, constitutional democracy tries to complement the weaknesses of constitutionalism and democracy.

Constitutional democracy has been a global phenomenon. Many countries have adopted a mix of constitutionalism and democracy in theory. Most countries around the world with so-called democratic systems basically should be sorted as constitutional democracies. It obviously shows the omnipresence of constitutional democracy (Murphy, 1993).

Constitutional democracy is sometimes referred to as liberal democracy. "Liberal" is derived from "liberty" and refers to a form of government in which individual rights and freedom are protected. Modern democracy is based on a liberal philosophy in which the role of the state is restricted by the constitution. Constitutional democracy is the government of laws rather than of men. Even elected rulers are subject to constitution that always includes a statement of individual rights. In theory and sometimes in practice, citizens can use domestic and international courts to uphold these rights when they are threatened or violated even by an elected government.

Civic Education

Civic education is an important component of education that cultivates citizen's capacity to participate in public democratic life and use their rights

and discharge their responsibilities with necessary knowledge and skills. Bennett (1993) notes that civic education is a project of creating a political culture which would instill in all citizens the attitude to protect the good values of their society. Civic education is the study of rights and duties of citizenship. In other words, it is the study of government with attention to the roles of citizens as opposed to external factors in operation and oversight of government.

The concept of civic education is not difficult to define. It is interesting to note that in this current era of globalization the term civic education is debatable among scholars. Nevertheless, civic education has not drawn scholarly controversy. Even the best of scholar would approach it as citizen's awareness and organizational effort to protect the common good of their political community, defend their rights and oppose any threat and or insecurity against the community. The meaning given here implies that civic education is a political culture characterized by most citizens' acceptance of the authority of the state as well as the general belief in participation in civic duties. This creates a kind of civic culture model. Perhaps, that is why Shklar (1991) one of the founders and theorists of American democracy rejected the idea of civic education. It is impossible, he says, to instill in all citizens a common opinion about what is good for the society, and a common passion to achieve it. At least he says, it is impossible to do this in a free society. However, educators throughout the world have recognized that civic education centered on teaching and learning the principles and practices of democratic governance and citizenship.

Civic education seeks to accomplish a number of general goals, such as impart knowledge about democratic practices and institutions, instill core democratic beliefs and values, encourage more active and informed political participation. National Orientation Agency (2009) asserts that democracy can be sustained by vibrant and responsive civic education that would promote

the ideals of nobility for a purposeful society which in turn would inculcate the needed positive values in Nigerian children to make them good citizens. For constitutional democracy to flourish, citizens must not only be aware of their rights, they must also exercise them responsibly and they must fulfill those personal and civic responsibilities necessary for a self-governing, free and just society.

Muhammed (2009) affirms that civic education is an integral and important aspect of smooth democratic transition that could provide avenue for qualitative participation of an average Nigerian in self-governing process as well as people oriented democracy. More importantly, through civic education, knowledge, skills and culture of enhanced democratic ideals would be realized and imbibed across the population.

The sustenance of constitutional democracy is therefore dependent upon the knowledge, skills and the dispositions of the citizenry. A nationwide initiative in civic education is deemed highly imperative. Such an initiative would promote civic literacy, foster civility among citizens, promote understanding and appreciation of democratic institutions and processes and enhance a sense of political efficacy.

Core Components of Civic Education and their Implications on Democratic Sustainability

Civic knowledge

Civic knowledge is concerned with the contents of what citizens ought to know, the subject matter. Civic knowledge is power. For democracy to work in Nigeria and in every nation of world, citizens must be informed and engaged. Sustainability of democracy lies in the capacity of citizens of all ages and from all backgrounds understanding of how government and political system work as well as their own rights and responsibilities.

Formal instruction in civics should provide a basic and realistic understanding of civic life, politics, and government (Parker, 1996). It should familiarize students with the constitution of their country and the state in which they live, because these and other core documents are criteria which can be used to judge the means and ends of government. Carter (1997), notes that the formal instruction in civics should emphasize the rights and responsibilities of citizens in a constitutional democracy. These rights have been categorized in various ways by Carter, but a useful and general accepted categorization divides them in this manner:-

- ? Personal rights such as freedom of thought, conscience, expression, association, movement and freedom of residence and privacy.
- ? Political rights such as freedom of speech, press, assembly, petition as well as right to vote and be voted for.
- ? Economic rights such as the right to acquire, use and transfer property, to choose one's work or change employment, to join the labour union or a professional organizations, to establish and operate a business, to obtain copyright or patent, and to enter lawful contracts.

Sustainability of democracy depends in parts on the knowledge and fulfillment of those personal and civic responsibilities by the citizens. Przeworski (1995), notes that civic knowledge is indeed power but action is essential. In other words, without civic action, civic knowledge can never ripen into truth. Civic knowledge consists of fundamental ideas and information that learners must know and use to become effective and responsible citizens of a democracy. In general, civic knowledge includes principles of democratic theory, operations of democratic governance and behaviours of democratic citizenship. In particular, it involves concepts and data about democracy in the learner's country and comparison with other countries (Quigley, 1994).

Civic Skills

The second essential component of civic education that can promote democratic sustainability is the civic skills. If citizens are to exercise their rights and discharge their responsibilities as members of a self-governing communities, they do not only need to acquire a body of knowledge but they also need to acquire relevant intellectual and participatory skills. Etzion (1995), notes that intellectual skills in civics are inseparable from content. To be able to think critically about political issues, one must have an understanding of the issue, its history, its contemporary relevance, as well as command of a set of intellectual tools or considerations useful in dealing with such issue. The intellectual skills essential for informed, effective and responsible citizenship sometimes are called critical thinking skills.

A good civic education programme enables one to identify or give meaning or significance to things that are tangible, such as, the National flag, national monuments, or civic and political events. Good civic educations also foster the skill of describing e.g. the ability to describe functions and processes such as legislative processes, judicial review, check and balances. Discerning and describing trends, such as participation in civic life, immigration or employment, helps the citizens fit current events into a long term pattern (Etzioni, 1991).

The civic skills that can promote democratic sustainability include skills of monitoring and influencing public policy. Monitoring skills refers to exercising oversight or "watchdog" functions on the part of the citizens. The participatory skills of influencing refers to the capacity to affect the processes of politics and governance, both the formal and the informal processes of governance in the community (Parker, 1996).

Civic Dispositions

The third core component of civic education, civic dispositions, refers to the traits of private and public character essential to the maintenance and

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sustainability of constitutional democracy. Civic dispositions, like civic skills, develop slowly over time as a result of what one learns and experiences in the home, school, community and organizations of civil society. These experiences should engender understanding that democracy requires responsible self governance of each individual; one can not exist without the other (National Commission on Civil Renewal, 1998).

Civic Dispositions at a Glance

Civic Disposition	American Standard Definitions
Patriotism	Being loyal to the values and principles underlying constitutional democracy, as distinguished from jingoism and chauvinism.
Open mindedness	Having respect for others' right to an equal voice in government, to be equal in the eyes of the law, to hold and advocate diverse ideas, and to join in associations to advance their views.
Negotiation and Compromise	Making an effort to come to agreement with those with whom one may differ, when it is reasonable and morally justifiable to do so.
Compassion	Having concern for the well-being of others, especially for the less fortunate.
Critical mindedness	Having the inclination to question the validity of various positions, including one's own.
Persistence	Being willing to attempt again and again to accomplish worthwhile goals.

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Respect for the Right of other individuals	Having respect for others' right to an equal voice in government, to be equal in the eyes of the law, to hold and advocate diverse ideas, and to join in associations to advance their views.
Respect for the law	Willingness to abide by laws even though one may not be in complete agreement with every law; willingness to work through peaceful, legal means to change laws which one thinks to be unwise or unjust.
Honesty	Willingness to seek and express the truth.
Tolerance of Ambiguity	Ability to accept uncertainties that arise, e.g., from insufficient knowledge or understanding of complex issues or from tension among fundamental values and principles.
Civic mindedness	Paying attention to and having concern for public affairs.
Courage	The strength to stand up for one's convictions, when conscience demands.

Source: (U.S. Centre for Civic Education, 1991)

Strategies for Developing Civic Knowledge, Skills and Dispositions in Learners

Cooperative Learning Activities

Through cooperative learning activities, learners develop various participatory skills and civic virtues associated with them. Learners involved

regularly in cooperative learning situations tend to develop such skills as leadership, conflict resolution, compromise, negotiation and constructive criticism (Slavia, 1991). They also develop such virtues as tolerance, civility and trust (Stahl Vansiokle, 1992).

The Use of Literature to Teach Civic Virtues and Dispositions

The study of literature, both fictional and historical exposes students to interesting people who exemplify civic virtues in dramatic situations. The characters in these stories therefore, may become role models for the students. At the very least, they are positive examples of a particular civic virtue that could help students understand the meaning and importance of morality in civic life. Stotsky (1992), an expert on using literature to teach civic virtues, stresses the educational values of exposing learners "to characters who exhibit such traits as courage, hope, optimism, ambition, initiative, love of country, love of family, a concern for the environment and outrage at social justice.

Active Learning Strategies

Civic knowledge, skills and dispositions or virtues can also be developed in the learners through active learning strategies. Examples of these active learning strategies include: systematic concept learning, analysis of case studies, role-play methods, dramatization method etc. Intellectually active learning of knowledge, in contrast to passive reception of it appears to be associated with higher level of achievement.

Conclusion

Civic education is essential to sustain constitutional democracy. Democracy is sustained by citizens who have the requisite knowledge, skills and dispositions. In other words, the ideals of democracy are most

completely realized when every member of the political community shares in its governance. To be effective civic education must be realistic. Citizens should be made to understand that if they are informed, effective and responsible, they are more likely to achieve personal goals for themselves and their families, as well as the goals they desire for their communities, states and nation.

Recommendations

Community service should be made an important part of civic education programme, provided it is properly conceived as being more than just doing good deeds. Community service should be integrated into both formal and informal curriculum of civic education. Community service is not a substitute for formal instruction in civics, but it can enhance that instruction. Schools therefore need to do more than making students aware of opportunities to serve their schools and community. Students need to be adequately prepared for experimental learning.

The importance of civic education should be communicated to the general public through televised public forums, print media, public announcements, parents, civic leaders etc. The media are important influences in disseminating information on civic education, and their support should be enlisted.

Participatory methods of teaching are critical to the success of civic education programmes. Role-playing, dramatization, small group exercises, group discussion etc. are far more result oriented.

In this globalized era, local resources for teaching civic education should be supplemented with the new information and communication technologies for better result and performance.

Capacity building programmes should be organized for civic education teachers at all levels.

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